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Co-author(s):	G. Paludetto (RSE), Z. Feng (UoS), A. Kontou (ICCS), O. Gehrke (DTU), T.A. Zerihun (SINTEF), A.G. Acosta (RWTH)
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List of Abbreviations

AIT	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology
API	Application Programming Interface
BESS	Battery Energy Storage Systems
CHIL	Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop
CVC	Coordinated Voltage Control
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DRTS	Digital Real-Time Simulation
GDRTS	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IP	Internet Protocol
JaNDER	Joint Test Facility for Smart Energy Networks with Distributed Energy Resources
JRA	Joint Research Activity
MU	Mobile Unit
NTP	Network Time Protocol
OLTC	On Load Tap Changer
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PNDC	Power Networks Demonstration Centre
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RI	Research Infrastructure
RiasC	Research Infrastructure as Code
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SoC	State of Charge
SPoF	Single Point of Failure
uAPI	Universal Application Programming Interface
UoS	University of Strathclyde
VILLAS	Virtually Interconnected Laboratories for LArge systems Simulation/emulation
VSI	Virtual Shifting Impedance
VSIDC	Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document reports on the integration and demonstration of advanced methods and services developed within the ERIGrid 2.0 project to realise extended Research Infrastructure capabilities. It also presents the work undertaken to implement tools for the Research Infrastructures integration and automation.

The objectives of this work are the following: *(i)* to implement methodologies and tools developed for improved laboratory coupling, *(ii)* to validate the improved laboratory coupling through simple tests, and to verify the performance and list the drawbacks of the implemented methodologies and tools, and *(iii)* integration of the configuration management and simulation setup automation system.

The document also presents an overview of the demonstrations, developed in the previous work and their detailed requirements. Subsequently, it provides details of all the methodologies and tools developed to enable improved laboratory coupling. This includes the Research Infrastructure as Code, laboratory middleware, configuration management, and Universal Application Programming Interface. Finally, a summary of known limitations of these tools and directions for future development and work are discussed as well.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document describes the implementation and validation of tools and methods for the integration of Research Infrastructures (RIs), within the scope of ERIGrid 2.0. It introduces the concept of the extended RI and how it is achieved using the demonstrations as outlined in Deliverable D13.1 (*D-JRA4.1 Description of the Test Cases, 2023*). Furthermore, tools and services to interconnect laboratories are discussed. This includes concepts such as Research Infrastructure as Code (RIasC) (details see Deliverable D11.1 (*D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods, 2023*) and Deliverable D11.2 (*D-JRA2.2 Software Release, 2023*)), distributed laboratory middleware, Universal Application Programming Interface (uAPI) (details see Deliverable 12.1 (*D-JRA3.1 Distributed Laboratory Middleware, 2023*)), etc. Through this, the capabilities of individual RIs can be extended to form a virtual one. An overview of the various tools and services is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of tools implemented. The lab coupling tools are shown in green, while the related JRA2 and JRA3 services are shown in orange and blue, respectively.

1.2 Extended Research Infrastructures

The major scope and focus of ERIGrid 2.0 is to interconnect RIs within Europe to perform joint smart energy experiments. This is done with the aim to fully utilise the strength and expertise of each individual RI (Pellegrino, Pala, et al., 2020). Hence, the laboratory coupling approach facilitates synergies amongst various RIs. By sharing hardware and software assets and associated knowledge from multiple RIs, newer and more complex test cases can be carried out on larger system configurations. This promoted technology development to realise the concept of virtually extended research infrastructures.

1.3 Relation to other Work Packages

The relation between the results of this work and other Work Packages (WPs) is depicted in Figure 2. As seen, this task builds upon the outcomes of the Joint Research Activity (JRA)2 and JRA3 WPs as well as on Deliverable D13.1 (*D-JRA4.1 Description of the Test Cases, 2023*) focused on test case descriptions. In this report, the key implementations of tools and methods to realise the previously developed test cases are summarised.

Figure 2: Relation between this work and other WPs.

1.4 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: An overview of all demonstrations is provided in Section 2. The technical details of tool implementation for RI integration are described in Section 3. Finally, conclusions and next steps are outlined in Section 4.

2 Overview of Demonstrations

To provide context for the reader, this section presents a concise summary of the demonstrations that were created as part of the JRA4 WP, along with their requirements in relation to the JRA2 and JRA3 WPs.

2.1 Demonstration 1: Improved Stability and Accuracy for PHIL

This demonstration seeks to improve both the accuracy and stability of Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) setups. To this end, it proposes an advanced interface algorithm which combines time delay compensation and shifting impedance with the additional advantage that the shifted impedance is virtually introduced in the hardware system. This results in a so-called Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation (VSIDC). This method is proposed to overcome the challenges related to the limited availability of hardware impedances.

The demonstration is implemented by applying the Virtual Shifting Impedance (VSI) method, developed in the frame of the JRA2 WP (details see Deliverable D11.1 (*D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods*, 2023)). The method was mathematically modelled and extensive analytical assessments and simulations have been carried out to study the properties of this method in terms of stability and accuracy.

The demonstration is to be conducted at the Power Networks Demonstration Centre (PNDC) of the University of Strathclyde (UoS). The experimental setup comprised a Digital Real-Time Simulation (DRTS) from RTDS technologies, a 270 kVA A bi-directional power amplifier, and a 50 kVA A passive load bank as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Overview of the PHIL experimental setup for Demonstration 1.

2.2 Demonstration 2: Time Delay Compensation

To support the pace of transition required by climate policy commitments, the complexity of power systems is increasing with the emergence of active power network controls, high penetrations of converter-interfaced distributed generation, new digitisation schemes, etc. Correspondingly, there is a growing need to find novel techniques for real-time simulation and Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) experimentation that can characterise the interactions between novel control schemes and emerging power technologies under a vastly greater range of operating conditions. Consequently, the concept of Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simula-

tion (GDRTS), as depicted in Figure 4, was proposed and explored to support the adoption of novel real-time simulation and HIL techniques for the whole energy system simulation across the geographically distributed RIs.

Figure 4: Representation of GDRTS setups for Demonstration 2.

In analogy to the conventional PHIL setup, the inherent time delay within the GDRTS closed-loop setup is variable yet deterministic and plays a detrimental role in the stability and accuracy of the GDRTS setup, where two or more DRTS are interconnected over the internet through a dedicated interface as leveraged in PHIL setups. The in-deterministic nature of the power signal data exchange through the internet not only results in a remarkably large time delay in the GDRTS closed-loop setup but also presents a remarkable challenge for the characterisation of the time delay and its consequential quantification and compensation, which are crucial for realising robust GDRTS with high-fidelity as outlined in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Representation of GPS-based time delay compensation for GDRTS setups.

As a key determinant of the stability and accuracy of the GDRTS, a comprehensive characterisation and in-depth analysis of the time delay is of great significance before the final-stage deployment of a GDRTS system. Moreover, advanced time delay compensation methodologies are important for robust GDRTS with precise power synchronisation and transparent power transfer across the candidate RIs. This test demonstration encompasses the following aspects:

1. In-depth assessments of the time delay compensation (i.e., Global Positioning System (GPS) based time delay compensation) developed in JRA2 WP regarding its capability in supporting active and reactive power transfer for smart grid applications.

2. Quantify the accuracy improvement of the GDRTS experiments adopted the following time delay compensation methods:
 - GPS based time delay compensation,
 - Probabilistic time delay compensation, and
 - Data-driven time delay compensation.
3. Experiment-based comparative performance evaluations of the aforementioned time delay compensation methods regarding their capability for providing delay compensation to the GDRTS setup.

2.3 Demonstration 3: Accelerated Time-to-Experiment for remote RI Testing

Distribution networks are becoming increasingly “smarter”, as well as more complex, with the addition of power electronic devices, Information and Communication Technology (ICT), smart meters, and more. As a result, advanced control strategies to manage such networks are becoming necessary. Testing these systems in their entirety is becoming a challenge which is progressively accomplished by distributing parts of the system between multiple RIs in order to cope with the increasing number of involved components and stakeholders such as grid operators, device manufacturers, market participants as well as regulators. However, distributed experiments represent a challenge in itself as the coordination of interactions between these participants is an additional burden added to the already complex system under test. This test case aims to demonstrate tools to accelerate the setup and the coordination of such distributed experiments.

As a use case, an optimal Coordinated Voltage Control (CVC) operating as a distribution management system is chosen. The algorithm manages all the devices of the network that are capable of regulating the voltage, either directly, for example, On Load Tap Changer (OLTC), or through the injection of active/reactive power, such as Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) and Photovoltaic (PV) inverters. Management is based on the solution of an optimisation problem, which minimises a predefined objective function, subject to linear and non-linear constraints.

Previous work has implemented this CVC algorithm in a central controller installed at the substation level. However, this has several drawbacks for the scope of this test case:

1. A centralised controller is not well suited to demonstrate the benefits of the tested tools for accelerating the setup of highly distributed experiments as the controller only consists of a single instance.
2. A centralised controller represents a Single Point of Failure (SPoF) in the distribution grid. An outage of the controller would result in a non-optimal configuration of the system leading to increased losses and costs. At the same time, maintenance of such control systems becomes more difficult if it needs to be conducted on a live system.

Hence, for this test, a distributed version of a CVC is used to provide redundancy and demonstrate the capabilities of a highly distributed experimental setup. To consider all possible scenarios regarding the availability of software and hardware from all the RIs, the test case will include DRTS interconnected with devices in Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL) and PHIL schemes, as depicted in Figure 6. Here, the multiplicity of the connecting arrows indicates the

number of devices. For instance, one DRTS will be used to simulate the distribution network, while n indicates that more than one CVC controller will be used.

Figure 6: Schematic representation of Demonstration 3.

The CVC controller is initialised with all the necessary static data of the network: network topology, admittance of lines and transformer, nominal power of Distributed Energy Resource (DER) units and storage systems, operating limits, tap positions of the OLTC, etc. While it operates, it requests and receives real-time power measurements from the smart meters of loads and DER units, as well as the State of Charge (SoC) of the storage systems and the current tap position of the OLTC. Using this dynamic data, it formulates the optimal power flow problem, whose objective function involves the minimisation of voltage deviation of critical nodes from the nominal value, power losses of the lines and transformer, and tap change operations of the OLTC.

The ability of the tools developed in the JRA2 and JRA3 WPs for interoperability and rapidly setting up and changing the configuration of distributed experiments is evaluated before and after implementing them in the use case, and getting the corresponding effort, namely time-to-experiment.

2.4 Demonstration 4: Multi-Energy District Flexibility

The integration of local energy systems has been recognised as a viable approach to addressing the difficulties posed by the widespread use of non-programmable Renewable Energy Sources (RESs). With this in mind, the purpose of this demo is to examine the technical feasibility of utilising power-to-heat in a local multi-energy district and to assess its impact on both the electric and thermal networks. By combining electric and thermal storage systems and incorporating flexible loads, such as heat pumps, thermal loads, and electric boilers, this demonstration will explore the ability of the heating system to offer services to the electrical system, including congestion management and balancing power provision. Figure 7 provides an overview of the electrical and thermal systems.

This demonstration represents a significant advancement in the field, as multi-energy districts are complex systems that are difficult to replicate in a laboratory setting. Furthermore, the

Figure 7: A schematic representation of Demonstration 4 is presented, highlighting its electrical system comprised of three primary feeders and a simulated grid component. The thermal domain models a district heating network.

demo offers a unique opportunity to perform hardware tests by integrating resources from different RIs, creating an extended RI with greater capabilities than any single laboratory.

Demonstration 4 will utilise tools developed in JRA2 and JRA3 WPs, emulating the multi-energy district by integrating equipment across multiple RIs. Data exchange among RIs will be facilitated by the tool developed in the JRA2 WP and managed through services provided by the JRA3 WP. In particular, for the data exchange Lablink and the uAPI (as described in Section 3) are used.

2.5 Demonstration 5: AC & ICT Co-Simulation

Smart grids and energy systems are characterised by complex interactions between the ICT domain and one or more energy domains. There are currently no established tool chains and validation approaches for the holistic validation of such systems.

Demonstration 5 characterises the properties of the co-simulation framework (details see Deliverable D11.1 (*D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods*, 2023)), for the simulation of interactions between electrical grids and ICT networks. This will be done by comparing the dynamics of the simulated system to those of two laboratory setups: (i) one where an electrical grid and (ii) an ICT network are emulated in real-time, versus real, physical networks.

This demonstration will be the first step towards a dedicated validation test, by exploring the range of achievable performances. It is currently unknown how accurate the co-simulation setup can be expected to reflect the physical reality. Therefore, the test focuses on a quantification of the measured deviations between simulation and reality, and on an identification of factors influencing the achievable accuracy. The data collected during the experiments would allow a reference scale (pass/fail) to be calibrated.

The demonstration case investigates a section of an electrical distribution grid with flexibility assets, each of which is included in the portfolio of one of two aggregators. The assets are

dispatched by the aggregators in response to flexibility service requests by the distribution grid operator. A heterogeneous communication network facilitates the data transfer between the distribution system operator, measurement equipment in the grid, flexibility assets, and aggregators.

The simulated system can be excited in two ways, by events (e.g., equipment failure or limit violations) in the communication network or in the electrical network. The testing will investigate the system response to both types of events since they are expected to result in different dynamics due to the unequal strength of the coupling between the two simulated domains.

Figure 8 provides an overview of this demonstration.

Figure 8: A schematic representation of Demonstration 5.

3 Implementation of Tools for RI Integration

This section discusses all the newly developed tools within the ERIGrid 2.0 project to conduct multi-RI experiments and integrate RIs. This includes the RlasC approach (cf. Section 3.1), the laboratory middleware (cf. Section 3.2), and the uAPI (cf. Section 3.4).

3.1 Research Infrastructure as Code

RlasC is a framework to accelerate distributed RI experiments, developed in JRA2.2. Inspired by the Infrastructure-as-Code paradigm (Quattrocchi & Tamburri, 2023), it aims to accelerate experiments by a high degree of automation of common tasks in a research environment. RlasC realises this by utilising existing cloud-computing technologies and applying them in a research environment to provide the following functionalities:

Provisioning of Mobile Units (MUs): A MU in RlasC's terminology is a mobile computing device acting as a gateway between laboratory equipment and other possible remote laboratories. The setup and maintenance updates of the units are handled by RlasC to alleviate the researcher from a manual setup of these devices.

Deployment of Containerised Software Components: The MUs run a Linux operating system and join a Kubernetes¹ cluster which consists of all the MUs. This Kubernetes cluster allows the research to declaratively describe the setup of software components which are executed as containerised applications on the cluster.

Transparent Inter-laboratory Overlay Network: Research of highly complex systems such as modern energy systems is increasingly undertaken by a group of researchers and institutions. Consequently, it is desirable to perform distributed experiments spanning multiple laboratories. RlasC simplifies the setup of such distributed setups by providing a transparent Internet Protocol (IP) overlay network between all participating laboratories.

Time Synchronisation: For GDRTS a common time-base is required in order to synchronise the simulation of coupled subsystems as well as the proper temporal alignment of simulation results. A time-synchronisation service provides this common time-base by synchronising the clock of each MU via one of the supported synchronisation sources. The RlasC time-synchronisation currently supports the GPS, the Network Time Protocol (NTP) or the Precision Time Protocol (PTP) as synchronisation sources.

Network Emulation: Network emulation allows for a realistic emulation of real-world network characteristics. RlasC provides a network emulation service which allows the researcher to declaratively describe desired network parameters such as communication delay, packet loss, throughput etc.

Network Monitoring: In a geographically distributed experiment which possibly spans across multiple laboratories, network characteristics are also affected by the communication link between the sites. In many cases, this is the public Internet and/or the national research networks. These networks are shared mediums and as such can exhibit congestion and unpredictable latencies and packet loss. RlasC aims to counteract these effects by providing a network monitoring service which monitors the network conditions between a configurable set of MUs. In a similar manner to the network emulation configuration, the scheduling of these monitoring tests can be configured declaratively.

¹<https://kubernetes.io>

Figure 9 illustrates an exemplary setup of three labs using RlasC. In this case three laboratories are coupled via a distributed Kubernetes cloud. RlasC uses K3S as its Kubernetes distribution which is optimised for lightweight deployments on edge devices which run the K3S agent process. In the ERIGrid 2.0 case, the consortium also refers to the agent nodes as MU. Each laboratory hosts one or more MUs which automatically join the cloud. To deploy a MU, an existing desktop or server workstation could be used. But also more lightweight single-board computers like the Raspberry Pi² can be used. The requirements for running a Kubernetes agent are relatively low. Both Intel/AMD x86 and ARM architectures are supported. K3S has no other external dependencies besides the Linux kernel. This is a main factor to simplify the whole deployment of new nodes.

Figure 9: Architecture setup of RlasC.

Further details and documentation can be found on the related RlasC website³. RlasC supports the application and usage of the subsequently discussed uAPI for easier multi-lab experiments.

3.2 Distributed Laboratory Middleware

The primary purpose of the “laboratory middleware” is to facilitate seamless data exchange between RIs for JRA. This can include, but is not limited to physical laboratories, real-time and non-real-time simulators, etc. Several existing developments cover parts of the intended scope, i.e., Joint Test Facility for Smart Energy Networks with Distributed Energy Resources (JaNDER) (Pellegrino, Sandroni, et al., 2020) from the ERIGridproject, Virtually Interconnected Laboratories for LARGE systems Simulation/emulation (VILLAS)framework (Monti et al., 2018), and AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)’s Lablink⁴. Therefore, the main objective of the

²<https://www.raspberrypi.org>

³<https://riasc.eu>

⁴<https://github.com/AIT-Lablink>

laboratory middleware is to harmonise all these tools under a common software platform. This is to be achieved by:

- Providing a transport-independent abstraction layer, such that it will be easy for a RI to switch from using for, e.g., JaNDER in one experiment to using VILLASframework in another. This prevents the need to implement multiple lab-to-transport interfaces and local adaptations to data formats, channel naming, etc.
- Developing new functionalities which none of the existing transport modules currently provides, but which the consortium finds desirable. These functionalities are to be developed as modular services.
- Moving common functionality which may exist in individual transport modules to the common framework, in order to avoid work duplication. For example, let us assume transport “A” has a sophisticated mechanism for time synchronisation, while transport “B” has a very rudimentary mechanism and transport “C” does not provide such a mechanism at all. Then, it could be considered to make a “synchronisation service” based on “A”’s solution available as part of the framework such that it could be used by other transports if convenient.

This overall architecture is illustrated in Figure 10, which highlights all these blocks. The infrastructure layer forms the bottom-most layer, consisting of physical laboratory infrastructures, hardware devices, Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems, etc. This layer is then connected to the platform layer that provides services, such as network emulation and provisioning. The software layer is present on top of these platform services and provides services, such as data exchange through aforementioned tools like VILLASframework, JaNDER, Lablink, etc. The uAPI provides a set of common functionalities for data exchange as services.

Figure 10: Distributed laboratory middleware framework, developed within the JRA3 WP.

Further details about the middleware approach are provided in the related Deliverable D12.1 (*D-JRA3.1 Distributed Laboratory Middleware*, 2023).

3.3 Data Exchange Tools

3.3.1 VILLASframework

The VILLASframework is a collection of tools for coupling test beds and real-time simulators between geographically distributed laboratories, originally designed for real-time simulation of electrical networks (Monti et al., 2018). It consists of several independent components, which can be combined according to the requirements and needed functionalities of the targeted experiment. The modular structure of the framework allows easy extensibility with new interfaces, protocols and data formats. This is supported by the open development approach, which makes the framework fully available as open-source software under the Apache 2.0 license to external users, allowing them to collaborate on the common code base. The overall architecture of the framework is shown in Figure 11. Further details can be found on the related code repository⁵.

Figure 11: Overview of the VILLASframework architecture.

The central component is *VILLASnode*, an interface/gateway for the coupling of involved components. *VILLASnode* is used as a real-time capable data exchange mechanism in the software layer of the developed laboratory middleware. All communication endpoints interfaced by the gateway are represented by *VILLASnode* instances of certain node types. Besides supporting common communication protocols (e.g., AMQP, MQTT, nanomsg, Kafka, FIWARE NGSI) and data formats, the gateway also allows direct interfacing with various open-source and commercial simulators like DPsim, OPAL-RT and RTDS. With its easy configuration and extensibility, *VILLASnode* supports the uAPI vision by providing a flexible multi-purpose gateway for data exchange between individual system components or entire RIs.

The framework further includes the *VILLAScontroller* component that allows configuration, in-

⁵<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/acs/public/villas>

ventory and control of involved laboratory infrastructure, which exchanges the current status as well as control commands and configurations between the virtual control room and the laboratory infrastructure. In addition, *VILLASweb* provides a web-based user interface with which scenarios, user groups, laboratory infrastructure and measurement results can be managed. The execution of experiments can be monitored and controlled by means of a freely programmable virtual control room. For this purpose, real-time data can be transferred directly to the web-based control room via the *VILLASnode* gateway.

3.3.2 JaNDER

This section introduces the implementation of middleware Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) using the JaNDER transport layer (Pellegrino, Pala, et al., 2020). Developed within ERIGrid, JaNDER facilitates data exchange between different RIs by means of a secure internet connection using HTTPS (Pellegrino, Pala, et al., 2020).

The main objective was to utilise JaNDER as a transport mechanism for information that aligns with the APIs data model. This standardised format enables interoperability among different transport services. JaNDER's core functionality is the replication of infrastructure data through a cloud node. When data is recorded in a local database, it is mirrored in the cloud database and vice versa. At this level, the data is simply transported without any interpretation of its structure.

Built on top of the replication software, a layer defining the data model for the exchanged measurements can be constructed. This layer makes the data model developed in JRA3.1 accessible to the user and maps the model class instances to the appropriate database data structures that need to be replicated. The architecture is depicted in Figure 12.

Figure 12: JaNDER transport equipped with uAPI, each RI is equipped with a local database instance connected to the cloud node.

The building blocks of JaNDER are the following ones:

- *Cloud Node*: Redis database⁶ in the cloud, serving as a platform for exchanging data between the various RI nodes. Access to the cloud node is secured using certificates and HTTPS protocol. It acts as the intermediary between the local nodes of the different RI instances.
- *RI Database*: A Redis database located at the facility that serves as the endpoint for data read and write operations. The replication software, if running, synchronises the data between the cloud and the local nodes.
- *Replication Software*: Developed in GoLang⁷, the software opens connections to both the local Redis node and the cloud node using secure certificates. It replicates data between the two nodes by subscribing to the Redis keyspace notifications and intercepting updates of keys matching a specific pattern. The replication can be conducted bidirectionally between local and remote nodes.
- *uAPI Middleware*: This component exposes the ERIGrid 2.0 APIs and communicates with the local Redis node by reading and writing information. The data model underlying the API is mapped to Redis keys for replication to the cloud node and accessibility across connected infrastructures.

At present, the implementation of the APIs enables the use of channels, samples, and events as specified in JRA3.1. The current implementation of the API enables JaNDER to operate in various infrastructures, with compatibility and interaction with different transport services still under development.

3.3.3 Lablink

Lablink⁴ is a tool that aims to make laboratory development and evaluation more efficient, flexible, and modular. It focuses on laboratory hardware and software equipment and seeks to automate tasks such as coupling components, logging results, and automating test cases. The software architecture of Lablink is depicted in Figure 13.

The core of Lablink is a middleware that handles communication among distributed clients. This middleware, called Lablink Core, provides data routing and encoding facilities. It is implemented as a distributed application and provides interfaces that expose the functionality of Lablink. Its core infrastructure serves as the foundation for creating dedicated Lablink clients, allowing access to common components such as laboratory hardware or simulation tools. Additionally, utility tools for synchronising clients or recording data can be implemented on top of the Lablink Core.

3.4 Universal API

The JRA3 uAPI is an API specification developed as part of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. It is designed to provide a universal solution for data exchange between laboratories. One of the key approaches of the ERIGrid 2.0 project is the coupling of laboratories, which allows for the sharing of hardware and software between different RIs. The uAPI supports this vision, enabling the creation of complex test cases on an extended system configuration. It is based on an open

⁶<https://redis.io/>

⁷<https://go.dev/>

Figure 13: Overview of the Lablink architecture.

API specified REST HTTP interface. Hence, each implementation of the uAPI is free to implement a subset of the endpoints specified within the API. The transports shall document which features are implemented and return a 501 "Not Implemented" HTTP status code in case an unsupported endpoint is used.

The goal of the uAPI is to harmonise some of the most used functionalities for multi-RI experiments. This can include functions such as GET values, SET values, etc., and can be better visualised through Figure 14. By implementing the uAPI once, each RI can use multiple transport tools, without the need to develop or code a new interface between their laboratory infrastructure and the transport tool.

Figure 14: Architecture overview of the uAPI.

3.5 Validation

All the aforementioned tools have been tested and validated using simple experiments. This includes the following:

- Data exchange tests using the uAPI between partners involved in Demonstration 4.
- RlasC has been tested and deployed in multiple partner laboratories to carry out Demonstrations 2 and 3. It uses the developed time-synchronisation and data-logging services.

3.6 Known Limitations

The laboratory middleware offers numerous advantages such as ease of deployment, modular architecture, wider support, etc. Nevertheless, it also has some limitations as listed below:

1. *Data-exchange Rate*: The laboratory middleware consists of multiple modular tools/services, typically operating at different rates. Hence, in the quest to harmonise some of these services, there exists a trade-off between ease of use and data-exchange rate. For example, as noted in (Syed et al., 2021), the type of applications that can be studied across multi-RI experiments is strongly influenced by the data-exchange rate. Furthermore, the uAPI is based on a REST-HTTP interface which is not designed for fast performance. Hence, this factor must be kept in mind when defining experimental test cases.
2. *Need for Laboratory Adapter*: Another shortcoming of the uAPI paradigm is the need for a “last-mile” laboratory adapter which is an interface between the laboratory infrastructure and the uAPI itself. The varying laboratory architectures and infrastructures within the consortium make this a challenge. Hence, a one-size fits all solution cannot work. Therefore, each RI must implement a software-based adapter between their RI and the uAPI. Nonetheless, it is expected to be a one-time implementation that works in conjunction with the uAPI for data exchange as a service.

4 Conclusions and Next Steps

The objective of this work is to implement and validate tools and methods for the RI integration automated management. To that end, this report presented an overview of the demonstrations and their associated requirements, developed within the JRA4 WP. Furthermore, this work shows the implementation and application of various tools from the JRA2 and JRA3 WPs for the RI integration, namely:

- Research Infrastructure as Code (RIasC) – JRA2 WP,
- Distributed laboratory middleware – JRA3 WP,
- Configuration management – JRA2 and JRA3 WPs, and
- Universal Application Programming Interface (uAPI) – JRA3 WP.

This report also documents the key requirements for the implementation of the demonstrations to be further carried out ERIGrid 2.0.

The implementation and validation of these tools and methods streamline the RI integration process. In addition, the development of the uAPI as part of the JRA3 WP efforts provides a common language for the integration of different RIs, further facilitating the process.

In summary, the work carried out in JRA4.2 lays a solid foundation for the realisation of the concept of the extended RIs and represents a significant step towards the integration of RIs on a larger scale. The next activities will build on this foundation by demonstrating the potential of these tools and methods in real-world multi-RI experiments.

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